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PERCEIVE

**Perceptive Enhanced Realities of Colored collections
through AI and Virtual Experiences**

D1.3 Quality Assessment Plan, Risks and IPR management

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2	FORTH	Foundation for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
3	ANAMNESIA	ANAMNESIA	France
3.1	IMKI	IMKI	France
4	NTNU	Norges Teknisk-Naturvitenskapelige Universitet	Norway
5	FRAUNHOFER	Fraunhofer Gesellschaft Zur Forderung Der Angewandten Forschung	Germany
6	MIC-MANN	Ministry of Cultural Heritage- National Archaeological Museum of Naples	Italy
7	OSL-MUNCH	Oslo Kommune Munch Museum (MUNCH)	Norway
8	AIC	The Art Institute of Chicago	USA
9	HOVERLAY	Hoverlay	USA
10	HSLU	Fachhochschule Zentralschweiz -Hochschule Luzern	Switzerland
11	V&A	Victoria and Albert Museum	UK

Executive Summary

This deliverable describes the quality assessment plan, risk mitigation strategy and intellectual property (IPR) management for the PERCEIVE Project.

Within this deliverable the quality assessment plan will be designed and established, following a procedure-based internal quality assessment system, including provisions for risk management, IPR management, assessment through performance indicators, collating and assessment of external feedback to ensure continued improvements in the project, internal audits, evaluation of the communication and dissemination efficacy, and consideration of gender and ethics issues.

The purpose of this deliverable is to serve as a guideline for the PERCEIVE project coordinator and consortium partners, in order to understand their responsibility and roles, to ensure the quality of various projects outputs and that reviews occur at appropriate points in the project. Whilst the details of specific quality related standards will be developed elsewhere in the project, the procedures for managing them are defined here.

In addition, this document includes a compendium of the legal and ethical codes that explain the handling of IPR when dealing with the digitization and analysis of cultural heritage objects in a multidisciplinary project such as PERCEIVE, where governmental and non-governmental institutions must collaborate and converge their various internal policies while at the same time abide by the national and EU legislations.

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1. Quality Assessment Plan

Quality assessment aids project management activities, so it guides the preparation of outputs and deliverables, so the objectives are met with success and work is of highest standards.

PERCEIVE consortium members are the target of this deliverable. The purpose of this deliverable is to illustrate the motivation of quality assessment and quality assessment procedures, empower and encourage WP teams and leaders to implement these procedures whilst performing their tasks. The success of each PERCEIVE objective will be measured through its respective KPIs.

The first sub-section will detail the Management Structure of the PERCEIVE project, this has been defined with more detail in D1.1 Operational Plan. The second sub-section will describe the Quality Management procedures for the different project outputs such as deliverables, as well as detail the Technical Quality Assurance plan, and Milestone Review plan. The third sub-section will detail the KPIs defined by the PERCEIVE project for each of the PERCEIVE objectives.

1.1 Management structure

1.1.1 General structure

The organisational structure of the consortium comprises the following Consortium Bodies:

- The **General Assembly (GA)** is the ultimate decision-making body of the consortium; GA is composed of one representative for each Party (beneficiaries and associated partners);
- The **Project Management Board (PMB)** is the supervisory body for the execution of the Project, which shall report to and be accountable to the General Assembly; PMB is chaired by the Project Coordinator and participated by the Scientific Coordinator, the Innovation Manager and WP leaders;
- The **Project Coordinator (PC)** is the legal entity acting as the intermediary between the Parties and the Granting Authority; PC shall, in addition to its responsibilities as a Party, perform the tasks assigned to it as described in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement.

Furthermore, the PERCEIVE project includes:

- A **Scientific Board (PSB)**, which plans, organises, and coordinates in general all research activities of the project, constantly overseeing the effectiveness in achieving the expected results and efficiently in carrying out the various activities on time, consulting when needed the WP leaders, the Advisory Board and the Management Board; it is chaired by the Scientific Coordinator and composed by the Project Coordinator, the Work Package (WP) Scientific Representative and one representative of each Working Group (if necessary, additional members might be appointed by the Project Committee);
- The **Advisory Board (AB)** which is composed by experts and innovators coming from main and representative institutions, whose role will be of advisors of the project: a minimum of 6 members every year are proposed by the Management Board and voted by the General Assembly, in line with the advancement of the project
- **Work Package Leaders (WPL)** are responsible for the coordination of the work of the partners, collaborating on that work packages. They are in direct and frequent contact with task leaders and the Project Coordinator, and make sure that deliverables are completed, while meeting the appropriate quality standards on time.

Figure 1

1.2 Quality Management

1.2.1 Project Outputs

The quality assessment is carried out for all project outputs.

Project outputs include:

- Periodic reports that include the scientific technical reports (R1: M1-M15) and (R2: M16-M36)
- Deliverables – see Section 1.2.2
- Other dissemination related outputs (as described in Deliverable 8.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10671131>)
 - Scientific and non-scientific publications
 - Newsletter
 - Videos
 - Website content
 - Press releases
 - Presentations and/or demonstrations
 - Educational material
 - Brochures

1.2.2 Roles and Responsibilities

The Project Coordinator (PC) is responsible for the quality control of the deliverables to the European Commission (EC), coordinated together with the Project Managing Board (PMB), defined in Section 1.1 Project Management.

Each contractual deliverable will be reviewed within its respective WP, prior to its submission to the Commission. A peer review by partners not directly involved in either the subject matter or the creation of the deliverable will also be conducted.

The Project Manager (PM) will make the final check of the deliverable to ensure consistency and readability before sending it to the PC for submission to the EC. To ensure that the deliverable complies with the project's contractual requirements, the PC could request further work on a deliverable by the partners.

1.2.3 Deliverable Review Process

The following time-plan is presented to ensure that this process is followed through:

1. A relatively complete draft of the deliverable should be made available by the allocated beneficiary at least [*two weeks*] before the due date.
2. The draft version should be available for peer review by a nominated partner chosen by the deliverable editor. The review should be completed within [*3 working days*]
3. If the editor approves the deliverable, they will add “Reviewed by” to the document history and it will be passed on to the PC who will submit it to the EC.
4. If the editor demands for corrections, the WP must address those. This process can be iterated.
5. Any comments should be integrated, and the final version must be made available to the PC [*1 week before*] the deliverable is due, for a final check.
6. The PC will upload the deliverable as a *.pdf file once it has been approved by the editor.
7. It is up to the beneficiary of the deliverable to ensure that the schedule is maintained.
8. If the WP leader knows that their team cannot meet the four-week deadline, the WP leader has to notify the PM six weeks prior to the deadline of the deliverable.

1.2.5 Quality Criteria for Deliverables

The quality of each deliverable will be assessed following specific criteria to ensure uniformity and consistency in the review process and to facilitate it. The quality criteria is outlined below:

1. **Consistency:** The content of the deliverable is consistent with the description of the task in the PERCEIVE Grant Agreement
2. **Compliance:** All aspects of the deliverable (described in the Grant Agreement) are fully addressed
3. **Objective consistency:** The objectives of the deliverable are in line with the PERCEIVE objectives
4. **Scope consistency:** The content of the deliverable is in line with the scope of the deliverable and are relevant to its target audience
5. **Accuracy:** The content of the deliverable is scientifically sound and supported by relevant and well-sourced references
6. **Clarity:** The language of the text is clear; it is in consistent English (whether US or UK); the text is unambiguous; the terminology is clearly explained; there are no spelling or grammar errors; any potentially sensitive information is appropriately phrased
7. **Technical consistency:** The deliverable is submitted using the relevant templates

1.2.6 Quality Criteria for Other Outputs

The other dissemination related outputs (described in detail in Deliverable 8.1: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10671131>) will also be reviewed before they are published. The review will focus mainly on compliance with available templates and quality criteria. These materials are not subject to deadlines nor formal submission requirements; thus, the review process includes

only one step, which is the delivery of the draft document by the dissemination leader, and a technical check by the management team.

1.2.7 Technical Quality Assurance

All PERCEIVE related outputs will use the PERCEIVE templates. These templates are available for all project partners in the Microsoft Teams SharePoint Platform. The templates provide general structures to be followed.

Deliverables:

1. Header
2. Project information
3. Executive summary
4. Document History
5. Table of Contents
6. Sections (including Introduction and Conclusion)
7. Subsections
8. Annex

Meeting minutes:

- Meeting name
- Date
- Place
- Version
- List of participants
- Agenda item
 - Work package(s) concerned
 - Speaker(s)
 - Summary of presentation and discussion
 - Reference documents
 - Conclusion(s)/decision(s)
 - Deadline (if applicable)

1.2.8 Milestones

The **progress of the milestones** is reviewed during the Project Management Board meeting and decisions can be made to ensure their completion, or to delay future activities until corrective actions are completed. WP leaders related to the milestone can also attend the meeting. The frequency of Management Board meetings is defined in D1.1.

Milestone / Name Review Nr	Work Package No	Lead Beneficiary	Means of Verification	Due Date (month)	
M1	Requirements Milestone	WP1, WP5, WP6, WP2, WP8	1-CNR	Delivered D1.1, D1.2, D1.3, D2.1, D2.2, D5.1, D6.1, D8.1, D8.2	9
RV1	FIRST REVIEW MEETING	<i>Brussels</i>		1st reporting period review	15
M2	Alpha Milestone	WP1, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP4	2-FORTH	Delivered D1.1b, D1.4, D3.1, D3.2, D3.3, D4.1, D5.2, D6.1b, D7.1, D7.2a, D8.1b	18
M3	Beta Milestone	WP1, WP6, WP2, WP8, WP3	5-Fraunhofer	Delivered D1.1c, D1.3b, D2.1b, D2.2b, D3.3b, D6.1c, D8.1b	24
M4	Final Milestone	WP1, WP5, WP6, WP7, WP8, WP3, WP4	4-NTNU	Delivered D1.1c, D1.2b, D1.3c, D1.4b, D2.3, D3.1b, D3.2b, D3.3c, D4.1b, D4.2, D5.2b, D6.1c, D6.2, D6.4, D7.1b, D7.2b, D7.2b, D8.1c, D8.3b	36
RV2	FINAL REVIEW MEETING	<i>TBD / Remote, virtual</i>		2nd (final) reporting period review	36

Table 1: List of Milestones

1.2.9 Evaluation of communication and dissemination efficacy

The Communication and Dissemination Strategy and Plan is developed as part of Deliverable 8.1. To evaluate the efficacy of this strategy, the results and Key Performance Indicators (**KPIs**) will be assessed regularly. The outcomes which will be evaluated are:

- *Scientific publications*
- *Scientific presentations*
- *Media coverage*
- *Social media*
- *Website*
- *Dissemination events*
- *Newsletter*

Additionally, engagement from stakeholders and pilot schools will be monitored, especially in the case of outcomes related to Know-How webinars and streaming lectures.

1.3 Key Performance Indicators (KPI)

1.3.1 PERCEIVE Objectives and KPIs

PERCEIVE has defined 5 main objectives for the project:

- 1) OB1. Make heritage science results accessible for immediate use and further development to Creative Industry sectors;

- 2) OB2. Improve museums curatorial approaches to the study of coloured collection through digital shared methodology and to the use of digital practices to exhibit them;
- 3) OB3. Improve colour reconstruction and prediction methodologies and workflow;
- 4) OB4. Widen the access and explore the use of coloured collections and digital artworks, involving visitors and citizens, improving their understanding and at the same time increasing their engagement with experiences that could be perceived as “authentic”
- 5) OB5. European Citizens re-appropriation of Coloured Collections, increasing awareness of their fragility and importance, through the development of “sense of care”, based on the sense of wonder, emotion and embodiment.

Each PERCEIVE objective has associated KPIs which will allow the verifiability and measurability of results. These will be exploited in Deliverable 8.2 designed around the innovation potential of the project, integrating the KPIs for impact measurement with targeted values, potential barriers and obstacles.

OB1. Make heritage science results accessible for immediate use and further development to Creative Industry sectors, including Computer Graphics specialists, Exhibition and Light Designers, Game companies.

KPI 1.1	Number of cultural institutes reached	Based on PERCEIVE Call measure and in accordance with Advisory Board (AB) guidelines, a set of cultural institutes are selected for testing Tools, Services and Prototypes	≥ 20
KPI 1.2	Number of creative companies reached	Based on the PERCEIVE Call and AB guidelines, a set of creative sector companies will be contacted for testing Tools, Services and Prototypes. At least 5 companies will be selected for testing the tools.	≥ 100 SMEs
KPI 1.3	Business Potential	Business potential of the PERCEIVE outcomes, in € for the next 10 years, in terms of: new business, improved market share and improved efficiency and profitability.	≥ € 10M
KPI 1.4	Platform Engagement Score (similar to Pendo PES)	Measurement of the engagement of PERCEIVE’s Platform (and Repository), in terms of platform’s Adoption (percentage of stakeholders that use PERCEIVE’s features), Stickiness (reusability of features) and Growth (exploitation expansion).	≥ 70%

OB2. Improve museums curatorial approaches to the study of colored collection through digital shared methodology and to the use of digital practices to exhibit them

KPI 2.1	Number of involved CH stakeholders	Refers to the number of museums and other CH parties that are using PERCEIVE’s tools and services for designing and executing curatorial activities.	≥ 20
KPI 2.2	Number of ICT tools adopted	Refers to the number of PERCEIVE’s Tools and Services that are used by CH stakeholders.	≥ 5
KPI 2.3	Number accesses to Guidelines and training	Refers to the number of downloads/on line to PERCEIVE guidelines and know-how online training	≥ 200
KPI 2.4	Time Reduction	Refers to the reduction of an activity’s required process time (e.g. exhibition design or photorealistic 3D	≥ 60%

		rendering), by the adoption and exploitation of the PERCEIVE features.	
KPI 2.5	Cost Reduction	Refers to the reduction of an activity's cost (e.g. exhibition design or photorealistic 3D rendering), by the adoption and exploitation of the PERCEIVE features.	$\geq 40\%$

OB3. Improve colour reconstruction and prediction methodologies and workflow

KPI 3.1	Reconstruction fidelity/quality	Quantitative evaluation of the restoration/ recolorization output by using Image Quality Assessment metrics: Structural Similarity (SSIM) and Blocking Peak Signal-to-Noise Ratio (PSNR-B).	SSIM: ≥ 0.9 PSNR-B: $\geq 45\text{dB}$
KPI 3.2	Reconstruction Subjective Rating	Empirical evaluation of the quality/ fidelity of the predicted restored artwork, carried out by specialist stakeholders.	$\geq 90\%$
KPI 3.3	Reconstruction Time Reduction	Refers to the reduction of a colour reconstruction process' required time, by the adoption and exploitation of the PERCEIVE Framework.	$\geq 60\%$
KPI 3.4	Number of simulated scenarios	Refers to colour simulation applications that will be provided to CH stakeholders through the PERCEIVE platform.	≥ 3

OB4. Widen the access and explore the use of coloured collections (and their restoration) and digital artworks, involving visitors and citizens (inside but also outside museums), improving their understanding and at the same time increasing their engagement with experiences that could be perceived as “authentic”

KPI 4.1	Nr of prototypes	Refers to the number of prototypes (that will include one or more modules) designed and ready to be tested	≥ 3
KPI 4.2	Nr of design tools	Refers to the nr of design tools in the toolkit ready to be used by designers and educators	≥ 3
KPI 4.3	Nr of users	Refers to the number of downloads or participants testing prototypes and toolkit in events or on line sessions	≥ 200
KPI 4.4	Time Reduction	Refers to the reduction of time needed to set up a digital application or develop a digital exhibit	by 60%
KPI 4.5	Cost Reduction	Refers to the reduction of costs due to the speeding of the process from ideation to market ready product creation (The European exhibition market size is expected to reach revenues of \$18 billion by 2025, growing at a CAGR of over 3% during the forecast period. However, the cost of a media exhibition is quite expensive (i.e. from 5K€ to 15K€ per m2 for a large media exhibition) and with COVID Impact, the profitability of a cultural exhibition is more and more complicated.	$\geq 25\%$
KPI 4.6	Increased public attendance	PERCEIVE's VR/AR technologies will help maintain participation. Moreover, the introduction of HYBRID coloured experiences where the physical and digital	$\geq 80\%$

		components are integrated would increase the innovation appeal of exhibitions and creative products in general	
KPI 4.7	Commercialisation of project outcomes and increase of revenues	PERCEIVE is a strong competitive differentiation in cultural areas. The company Museum Factory wants to commercialize PERCEIVE results with licencing to their customers. As an example, one of the partners, the Museum Factory group including ANAMNESIA, a French leading company in cultural exhibitions, plans to increase annual revenues. This first exploitation, with other partner companies, demonstrates the interest of such an innovative solution in the cultural sector. This could also be deployed internationally for a large exploitation, and societal and economic impacts.	≥ 15%

OB5. European Citizens re-appropriation of Colored Collections, increasing awareness of their fragility and importance, through the development of “sense of care”, based on the sense of wonder, emotion and embodiment.

KPI 5.1	Increased participation	It refers to the numbers of testing users of the prototypes among users of different targets, but also among professionals and decision makers to analyse the potential impact on future decisions (such as on increase of interest and funding campaigns toward preservation/restoration)	≥ 200
KPI 5.2	Development of sense of care	It refers to parameters of engagement and sense of care identified during the project and evaluated in the assessment tasks. Analysis regarding the engagement will be defined and used as reference for this KPI	≥ 30%

2. Risk Mitigation

The following table describes the comprehensive Risk Mitigation strategies employed by PERCEIVE across various work packages, addressing critical aspects such as coordination, data acquisition, technological shifts, and external factors like pandemics, all with the aim of safeguarding the project's objectives and fostering its transformative impact. For each risk, we defined three assessment scales, according to its likelihood, its seriousness and a combination of the two. We have developed a “risk assessment and management spreadsheet tool” to support risk mitigation (For the full table, please refer to the supplementary file available in Annex 1).

Assessment scale		Status scale	Grade scale	
L	low	Current	A	neither likely, neither serious
M	medium	Obsolete	B	likely, but not too serious
H	high		C	less likely, but serious
E	extreme		D	highly likely, highly serious

Table 2: Scales used for assessing the urgency and importance of a risk

ID	Status	Date	Registered by	Risk	WP involved	Description	Assessment of Likelihood	Assessment of Seriousness	Grade (combined Likelihood and Seriousness)	Mitigation
Risk-1	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Coordination Failure	WP1	There is a critical risk that coordination in WP1 may fail to effectively manage the project.	L	E	C	The coordination is divided into financial and administrative aspects, as well as scientific coordination. Additionally, an innovation manager is appointed to enhance overall project management.
Risk-2	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Wrongly Elaborated Requirements	WP2	A potential risk in WP2 involves the wrongly elaborated requirements.	M	M	B	To address this, the project adopts an iterative path to understand end users' needs. Mitigation includes expanding stakeholder involvement, considering third parties and advisory board partners to set up target groups, and providing specific training for museum staff to guide and control project phases effectively.

Table 3: A snapshot of the spreadsheet tool for risk assessment and management

3. IPR Monitoring

One of the premises of PERCEIVE is to create a set of innovative tools, services and prototypes that simulate and explain the process of colour change in heterogeneous collections of artworks: statues and sculptures (WG1), paintings (WG2), textiles (WG3), and historic films (WG4). These tools, services and prototypes are informed by scientific measurements of the artworks' materials and the physical process underlying their degradation but could take various implementations of both scientific and artistic nature, as well as tangible and digital manifestations that are intended to become part of the final outcome of the project, an open museum (WG5) to be presented in a final exhibition. Although digital is the primarily targeted medium, hybrid experiences are targeted that consider mixed reality experiences (WP6). The complexity of data gathered, the data acquisition methods as well as the processing techniques represent intellectual property, and this section of the deliverable will discuss the matters regarding the intellectual property rights (IPR).

Intellectual Property Rights (IPR) stands for the collection of creative and innovative ideas or products produced by people. These rights are protected by a set of legal and ethical codes with various levels of reinforcements, as follows: copyright, trademarks, patents.

The most important international treaties for IPR include:

- **The Berne Convention**, administered by the World Intellectual Property Organization (WIPO) that deals with the protection of works and the rights of their authors (Wirth, 2001).
- **The Universal Copyright Convention (UCC)**, developed by UNESCO as an alternative to the Berne Convention for those states wishing to participate in copyright protection policies but disagree with aspects of the Berne Convention (Correa, 2000).
- **The TRIPS Agreement (Trade Related Intellectual Property Rights)** which is Annex 1C of the Marrakesh Agreement Establishing the World Trade Organization, signed in Marrakesh, Morocco on 15 April 1994 (Council Directive, 1994).

3.1 IPR for Cultural Heritage and its Digitization

Regarding Cultural Heritage, the increase in digitization capabilities and possibilities of online dissemination in the last 20 years raised many concerns for the lack of adequate legal protection. For instance, the online upload of high-resolution 3D data of an artwork together with disclosing sensitive information about its materials and composition might be a catalyst to unwanted consequence such as mass reproduction, commercialization, and commodification of cultural heritage and even the creation of forgeries and illicit trade on the art market (Ciortan, 2022). For this reason, regulatory

bodies in the cultural and legal sectors have proposed several legislations, policies and guidelines that are shortly described below:

- **Directive (EU) 2019/1024**, also known as “**the Open Data Directive**”

The Directive applies to documents held by **libraries**, including university libraries, museums and archives but excludes other cultural establishments (Article 1(2)(h)). It deserves emphasis that the selected institutions are considered holding a significant amount of valuable public sector information resources, especially thanks to digitisation projects (recital n. 65). Therefore, **notwithstanding the constraints deriving from intellectual property rights**, these documents shall generally be re-usable for commercial or non-commercial purposes and subject to principles such as openness by design and by default, transparency, and information duties. However, these institutions are also subject to a few specific derogations, i.e., they can charge for re-use (Article 6) and conclude exclusive arrangements for the digitisation of cultural resources (Article 12).

- **Directive on copyright in the Digital Single Market, Directive (EU) 2019/790 (CDSMD)**

Article 14 of CDSMD is of special interest for the topic of digitisation and digital preservation, as it introduces a new rule for the reproductions of works of **visual art in the public domain**, which is essentially addressed at the digital environment (recital n.53 CDSMD). Although several doubts regarding its correct interpretation (i.e., the definition of works of visual art is not provided) and overlap with existing national laws, establishing that any material resulting from an act of reproduction shall not be subject to copyright or related works, the provision aims at providing not only users but also cultural heritage institutions with enhanced legal certainty in the design of new practices of digitisation and dissemination of contents online.

- **The Maastricht Treaty of European Union (Article 128.1992 – Article 151.1997 – Article 167.2007)**

Article 128 was first introduced by the Treaty on the European Union, Official Journal C 191, 29 July 1992. Article 128 became article 151 after the Amsterdam Treaty (1997) due to re-numbering, and article 167 after the Lisbon Treaty (2007).

The Maastricht Treaty was the first legal document to establish clear competences in culture through the inclusion of article 128. Article 128, considered the first genuine attempt for cultural policy at the European level, emphasizes culture and the priority given by the European Union to its preservation and dissemination.

- **The Directive 93/7/EEC (1993)**

Council Directive 93/7/EEC of 15 March 1993 on the return of cultural objects unlawfully removed from the territory of a Member State OJ L 74, 27.3.1993, p. 74–79.

The Directive 93/7/EEC states that any object categorized as a part of the national treasures with artistic, historical and archaeological value, is a “**cultural object**” **dependable to the national legislations**. A cultural object is considered to be any object listed in the inventories of museums, archives or libraries’ conservation collections as well as the inventories of ecclesiastical institutions (Tsivolas, 2014).

- **Council Regulation (EC) No 116/2009**

Council Regulation (EC) No 116/2009 of 18 December 2008 on the export of cultural goods, entered into force 2 March 2009, OJ L 39 of 10.2.2009 of 18 December 2008 on the export of cultural goods, entered into force 2 March 2009, OJ L 39 of 10.2.2009, that repeals Council Regulation (EEC) No 3911/92 of 9 December 1992 on the export of cultural goods:

In order to ensure that exports of cultural goods are subject to uniform checks, this Regulation makes the presentation of an export license compulsory for their export outside the customs territory of the Community.

- **CETS No.018 / European Cultural Convention**

Treaty open for signature by the member States and for accession by European States which are not member States (<http://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/018>)

The purpose of this Convention is to develop mutual understanding among the people of Europe and reciprocal appreciation of their cultural diversity, to safeguard European culture, to promote national contributions to Europe's common cultural heritage respecting the same fundamental values and to encourage the study of the languages, history, and civilization of the Parties to the Convention. The Convention contributes to concerted action by encouraging cultural activities of European interest.

- **CETS No.019 / European Convention on Offences relating to Cultural Property, (Delphi, 23/06/1985 - Treaty open for signature by the member States and for accession by non-member States)** (<http://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/119>)

Based on the concept of common responsibility and solidarity in the protection of European cultural heritage, the Convention aims to protect cultural property against criminal activities. To achieve this objective, the Parties undertake to enhance public awareness of the need for protection, to cooperate in the prevention of offences against cultural property, to acknowledge the seriousness of such offences and to provide for adequate sanctions or measures with a view to co-operating in the prevention of offences relating to cultural property and in the discovery of cultural property removed.

- **CETS No.121 / Convention for the Protection of the Architectural Heritage of Europe (London, 1969, revised in Valetta 1992)** (<http://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/121>)

The main purpose of the Convention is to reinforce and promote policies for the conservation and enhancement of Europe's heritage. It also affirms the need for European solidarity regarding heritage conservation and is designed to foster practical co-operation among the Parties. It establishes the principles of "European co-ordination of conservation policies" including consultations regarding the thrust of the policies to be implemented.

- **CETS No.199 / Council of Europe Framework Convention on the Value of Cultural Heritage for Society (Faro, 2005)** (<http://www.coe.int/en/web/conventions/full-list/-/conventions/treaty/199>)

This Convention is based on the idea that knowledge and use of heritage form part of the citizen's right to participate in cultural life as defined in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights. The text

of the Convention presents heritage both as a resource for human development, the enhancement of cultural diversity and the promotion of intercultural dialogue, and as part of an economic development model based on the principles of sustainable resource use.

More recently, between 2020 and 2023, a Horizon 2020 project, entitled **reCreating Europe** (<https://libereurope.eu/project/recreating-europe-rethinking-digital-copyright-law-for-a-culturally-diverse-accessible-creative-europe/>) gathered experts from the legal and cultural sectors to refresh the digital copyright law that dictates the generation, access, and consumption of cultural and creative products. The project proposed a set of guidelines and recommendations for copyright applicable to the galleries, libraries, archives and museums (GLAM) sector:

- [Final Policy Recommendations for EU Lawmakers on Copyright in the GLAM \(Galleries, Libraries, Archives and Museums\) sector](#).
- Guidelines and Frequently Asked Questions on Copyright in:
 - [Galleries and Museums \(GMs\)](#)
 - [Libraries and Archives \(LAs\)](#)
- [Best Practices for Stakeholders and Policy Recommendations on the utilisation of Copyright Flexibility for increased Access to Digital Culture](#)
- reCreating Europe Final Conference Booklet - [Final Project Results, Outputs and Policy Recommendation](#)

3.2 The Scope of the IP Policy for PERCEIVE

The PERCEIVE IP policy covers:

- The individual & joined ownership for:
 - Software and software components
 - Patents
 - Unpatented inventions & discoveries
 - Methods of research and development and their artefacts
 - Data, assets and synthetically generated research data
 - Digital Cultural Heritage assets
 - Publication
 - Copyrights and trademarks
- The rights and obligations attached to it
- The evolution of the IP over the time of PERCEIVE project, from the background to the foreground
- The partnerships, overall exploitation & spin-off initiatives

3.3 Target Audience

In order to better deal with IP management, PERCEIVE has identified a strategy.

Each member of PERCEIVE consortium should name an **IP Manager (IPM)**, who will both be the operational manager and be accountable for:

- The IP (see PERCEIVE IP scope in §3.2 of this document) for the organization he/she represents
- Leading required negotiations about nature of IP

- Actions plans follow-up, including meetings, deliverables that are required for the definition and management of the PERCEIVE IPs

Each participant of each member of the consortium should have a good knowledge of the PERCEIVE IP management policy involvements, therefore should attend to a presentation of the contents of this document by the IPM.

3.2 Towards an IPR Management in PERCEIVE

3.2.1 IPR of Data Collection

Several case studies in PERCEIVE are **public domain** artworks, whose authors have died more than 70 years ago as is the rule under European copyright law. Article 14 of the CDSMD mentioned in section 3.1 of this deliverable has specific provisions for public domain artworks. The Article establishes that EU Member States shall provide that any material deriving from **acts of reproduction of works of visual arts in the public domain** shall not be protected by copyright or related rights. Nonetheless, **the implementation of this provision can vary with national legislation and IPR**. As stated in the Guidelines and FAQs for GM industries of reCreating Europe project (<https://zenodo.org/records/7586081#.ZCQASXZBy3A>):

*“Since they often partner with private companies, libraries, including university libraries, museums and archives can conclude agreements for the digitisation of cultural resources that would grant private parties exclusive rights on digitised resources, to allow them to recoup their investments. Exclusive rights can be granted, although limited in time and, in any case, subject to periodic review. Limits are established «to comply with the principle that public domain material should stay in the public domain once it is digitised» (recital n. 49 of the Open Data Directive, Directive EU 2019/1024). Yet, the application of such rules is subject to, amongst others, **intellectual property and data protection laws.**”*

For instance, ***The Scream (cca 1910) from the Munch Museum’s collection***, one of the case studies of PERCEIVE, has been part of the public domain since 2014 because the artist Edvard Munch died in 1944. Nonetheless, the museum policy states that the photographer or creator of digital content holds intellectual property rights for the visual reproduction of the painting and the name of photographer should be referenced, whenever the image is used. Thus, if a third party carries out high resolution digitization of the painting, the museum must pay for the right to use the given digitization. When it comes to the images taken by the museum photographers and displayed in the online gallery on the museum’s website, they can be used **under a Creative Commons license with the following terms and conditions:**

“The images here are available for free noncommercial use according to the [CC BY-NC-SA 4.0](#) license. In addition, they can be used for books, journals and similar material. kindly credit the museum by giving the name of the artist, the title of the work, the date, and the photo credit, like this: «Edvard Munch, The Scream (1910?). Photo © Munchmuseet / photographers name (if stated) ». If you need higher resolutions contact us at foto@munchmuseet.no”.

Similarly, the **digital images of Cezanne’s *Road in Provence*** from the website of Art Institute of Chicago can be shared under a CC0 license.

Nonetheless, the data collection in PERCEIVE goes beyond 2D color visual reproductions of the objects and will include **more complex analytical and 3D data** that require IPR. Thus, the

dissemination and sharing of such data will be evaluated on a case-by-case basis and agreed upon with the members of the consortium, also considering the national laws.

Regarding other types of digital data, such as **digital personal data** for evaluation purposes (data collected by PERCEIVE as part of the identification of stakeholders needs -WP2- and quality assessment activities -WP7), the project will comply with the EU data protection laws (i.e., GDPR, Regulation EU 2016/679) whenever personal data is collected and processed.

Moreover, because “processing of personal data can characterise different activities within the digital preservation project (for instance, personal data may be included in the digital object, or accessing and sharing the digital object may involve the processing of personal data of online users)”, data protection will be ensured as well when user will be interacting with the PERCEIVE digital platform. This is because “the major challenge for data protection and digital preservation is represented by the fact that **personal data is often implied in the use of digital technologies** (e.g., website cookies, data requests). Thus, cultural heritage institutions must comply with personal data laws (e.g., principles of lawfulness, information, data minimisation and security), from the early design phase (cf. principle of data protection by design and by default) when they engage in digital preservation” (reCreating Europe, 2023).

Two main methods will be used for data protection: **anonymization** and **pseudonymization**, as recommended by the reCreating Europe guidelines for GM industries:

“Since data protection laws apply when personal data are processed, the anonymization of personal data is often considered for compliance, next to pseudonymization. However, depending on the dataset, anonymization can be of high technical complexity and could require significant resources. Often, at the current technological advances and according to the legal doctrine, anonymization cannot relieve from compliance with data protection rules.”

3.2.2 IPR of Tools, Services and Prototypes

PERCEIVE consortium members, comprising of the technical and non-technical partners will be consulted to decide on the access, guidelines of use and sharing policy for the data, tools, services and prototypes that will be gathered, designed and developed during the project. Different access and use strategies according to the PERCEIVE IP policy might be created according to the typology of user (academic institution, governmental/non-governmental, company, etc.) and purpose of use (commercial/non-commercial). The policies should be planned according to a timeline that considers the duration of the project as well as the period after the project is concluded. For the management of the IPR a dedicated IP Map has been designed that allows for the management of IPR issues related to the Foreground provisions of each partner. This will agree with sustainable principles for digital data preservation and data management plan (DMP).

3.2.3 The PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM)

The PERCEIVE IP map is the synthetic view of all the assets that are, should or may be under IP policy.

It has 2 goals:

- Be a collaborative support to the convergence toward a global and agreed IP policy for all PERCEIVE components.
- Give a synthetic state of the IP consensus inside the PERCEIVE consortium at date

The PERCEIVE IP Map contains:

- The assets and assets components, according to their anteriority category (**background, foreground** or **post-project**)
- The **potential collisions** - and collision rating - between members' intents:

- The **current IP policy intention** or position of each member regarding the global policy can be expressed according to 3 levels:
 - o **Low limit:** limit under which the IP policy is not acceptable at first glance
 - o **Ok:** the global policy is satisfying
 - o **Ideal:** this would be the perfect target for the consortium member

IP Policy	
0	Out of my Scope
1	Wish unrestrictive use/free/open source etc.
2	Wish a restrictive use; eg consortium members or partially open source
3	Wish a co-proprietary policy
4	I am the exclusive owner

- The nature of IP the member would like to create:

Hereby indicating the different paths for IPR generation.

A first design of the PERCEIVE IP Map, that will be completed in detail by each member of the PERCEIVE consortium during the project is presented below:

Asset List	Collisions	Global IP Policy	Nature of IP
<p>01 - Knowledge generated and developed before</p> <p>02 - Knowledge generated and developed during</p> <p>03 - Knowledge generated and developed after</p> <p>04 - Other</p>	<p>01 - None</p> <p>02 - Minor</p> <p>03 - Major</p> <p>04 - Blocking</p>	<p>0 - Out of my Scope</p> <p>1 - Wish unrestrictive use/free/open source etc.</p> <p>2 - Wish a restrictive use; eg consortium members or partially open source</p> <p>3 - Wish a co-proprietary policy</p> <p>4 - I am the exclusive owner</p>	<p>0 - None</p> <p>1 - Copyright</p> <p>2 - Patent</p> <p>3 - Trademark</p> <p>4 - Creative Industries</p> <p>5 - Confidential information</p> <p>6 - Other</p>

Global View of IP Map (extract)

For the full table, a specific spreadsheet tool has been created (D1.3-IP management.xls).

As defined in D8.3 the list of assets and outcomes has been updated. During the upcoming months until M18 the consortium aims to complete this tool during its work on the IPR management and exploitation plans.

3.4 The Process of Convergence

The precondition for starting the process of convergence is the existence of the “Background assets” deliverable, which is already initialized at today’s date.

The process of convergence consists of 4 steps:

Step 1: Initialization by each member (M12)

Step 2: Negotiations until all blocking points are resolved (M18)

Step 3: Negotiations until most of the major points are resolved (M24)

Step 4: Continuous iterations on the IP map during the lifetime of the PERCEIVE project (>M24)

3.4.1 Initialisation

We propose the start of the Initialization as of delivery of this deliverable. New assets have been identified during the project requirements stage and the suggestion for demonstrations (see. D8.3), that will be incorporated into the asset list and require thorough IP Management.

It consists in a first round where each of the consortium members will fill out and complete the designed IP map according to

- its own assets,
- its own needs regarding the other’s assets,
- its own plans

Regarding the future of all the assets, and its intentions such as commercialization, start-up creation, joint ventures etc.

The map will be produced under the responsibility of the appointed IPM.

For this phase, it is important to keep 2 points in mind:

- The Global Policy of IP column is required but the Nature of IP column can be left for later on
- It is better to express some intentions, even wrongly than refraining from filling the Map since:
 - since a structured next step of discussion between the members will take place,
 - it will be much more effective to converge (modify/restrain some of the initial intentions) than diverge (add unexpected intentions late in the process).

A spreadsheet shared inside the consortium sharepoint will be setup for this purpose by the coordinator of WP1 and later in the process of WP8. Once done, the coordinator will evaluate the number and level of collisions between the members and update the spreadsheet.

Important note: any asset that would not be included inside this document before the end of key steps would be considered as a low importance request, as follows:

- **Blocking point after the end of step 2 or step 3:** the author should ensure that no collision due to Blocking points is created. In case of an irreconcilable collision, the added asset should be given an IP policy rating that is compatible with the existing wills of the other members, unless a dedicated negotiation with the impacted members is successful.

- **Blocking point after the end of step 4 (i.e. end of the project):** cannot be included into the IP map, unless a dedicated negotiation with the impacted members is successful.

3.4.2 Negotiation

Whenever some collision arises inside the P-IM, during the Steps 2, 3 or 4, there is an explicit obligation for the consortium to reach an agreement on the specific asset upon which there is a divergence of intentions. As an illustrative example, let us consider the following IP case (constructed case):

The Service Platform, which will clearly be a result of the commitment and efforts of each member of the consortium, may be a good subject of divergence regarding IP (the positions here expressed should not be considered as the real intention of any PERCEIVE member, but as an artificial example):

- *Academic Partner 1 wants the Platform to be fully open-source in order to create a wide community of contributors, which is viewed by Academic Partner 1 as absolutely necessary for the vitality and future of PERCEIVE, and for the gathering of experimental data [level 1 “Ok” in the extract of P-IM below - #1]*
- *Company 1 wants the Platform to be a paying SaaS service, with a cost/user/month within the range of 15€/20€ [level 3 “ok” in the P-IM below - #2], but would accept a freemium offer composed of an open source PERCEIVE Core Service, which could be useful for research purposes, but not sufficient to deliver the end-user value of PERCEIVE: the full use-case would require to buy a functional module, in paying SaaS mode [level 2 “Low limit” in the P-IM below - #3]*
- *Academic Partner 2 agrees with Academic Partner 1, but would prefer a restrictive use, because as PERCEIVE project will achieve its goals, 2 of their members’ plan to create a spin-off, together with Company 1 [level 1 “Ok” in the P-IM below- #4] and [level 2 “Very good” in the P-IM below - #5]*
- *Company 2 considers that the Platform is theirs and is not ready to share any ownership on PERCEIVE [level 4 “Low limit” in the P-IM below- #6] (as example).*

Asset				Global IP policy																	
				AP1	Comp1	AP2	AP3	Comp2	Comp3	Comp4											
				Collisions																	
Anteriority	Main owner	Asset name & short description	Component of asset	Low limit	Ok	Ideal	Low limit	Ok	Ideal	Low limit	Ok	Ideal	Low limit	Ok	Ideal	Low limit	Ok	Ideal	Low limit	Ok	Ideal
Foreground	All	Platform		1	2 3	3 3	1 2	4	3	3											
				#	#2#3	#4#5	#9	#6	#7	#8											

Simulation Exercise on P-IM

The IPM coordinator will setup a dedicated meeting where:

- Each member should present a set of slides (10 max) explaining its position
- The members will design a middle lane across the positions, generally representing the best overall value for the consortium members.
- Of course, it cannot be excluded that one or two extreme positions (such as the one by Company 2 in our previous example) would be considered by the qualified majority of the members as non-acceptable, therefore rejected.

In our example, the negotiation may lead to consensus on 2 (restrictive use, partially open source) or on 3 (co-proprietary), the position of the Academic Partner 1 and the Company 3 being considered as too extreme.

3.4.3 Continuous Iteration

After closing Step 2 which consists in eliminating all the blocking collisions, negotiations meeting will be planned according to the importance of the remaining major and minor collisions.

After closing the Step 3, which consists in eliminating most of the major collisions, negotiations meeting will be planned according to the importance of the remaining major and minor collisions.

It will be likely that new ideas, new business opportunities and evolving wills will emerge all along the PERCEIVE project. The P-IM should then be updated, the collisions identified, and new negotiation meeting planned.

The general principle in that case should be:

“A new IP proposition/need cannot represent a step backwards from the current P-IM state: a new proposition can comply with one of the 3 following cases:

- *adds a new IP asset or element,*
- *enlarges the possibilities of existing IP,*
- *there is an implicit consensus on the modifications of the P-IM as a consequence of a new IP proposition. But if it generates a Blocking and irreconcilable collision, the previous version of the P-IM prevails. “*

4. Consideration of ethics and gender issues

4.1 Gender Dimension

No specific evidence has emerged in terms of gender differences in perceiving colored artworks and in the related design research. Nevertheless, there are some studies that highlight some potential accessibility issues, with men being at higher risk for being born with colour blindness than women, who seldom have the problem (Birch 2012). An estimated one in ten males has some form of colour deficiency. Colour blindness is more common among men of Northern European descent. For this reason, the studies in WP7 will also take this issue into consideration. In Scientific literature there are no contributions to date about emerging differences between the genders to virtual experiences and to co-creation activities. Nevertheless, psychophysiological studies of perception (Sabatinelli et al. 2004, Lang et al., 1998) have also shown that the activation of brain areas can be different between genders when exposed to technology and content to stimulate creativity, thus resulting in different effects that, now, cannot be properly evaluated. However, to have a good gender balance, the consortium will make all efforts to organize user analysis, training, assessment sessions for the PERCEIVE platform with its Tools, Services and Prototypes with an equal number of males and females.

5. IPR Management Strategy

This section provides the final IPR management strategy for PERCEIVE, with a specific focus on the digital tools and services realised by the PERCEIVE Consortium and described as Key Exploitable Results (KERs) in D8.2 (e.g. PERCEIVE Platform and API, Color Knowledge Repository, PERCEIVE Prototypes, Design Toolbox, CoDesign Tool, Color-change simulation and rating tools). It translates the general framework defined in Section 3 (IPR Management) into concrete rules and default licensing intentions per result category, aligned with the exploitation plans.

5.1 Summary of the IPR challenges

PERCEIVE faces a set of specific IPR challenges:

- **Heterogeneous asset types**
 - Software (platform, API, web applications, simulation tools).
 - Data (3D models, images, multispectral and spectral data, appearance measurements, annotations, survey data).
 - SW-/HW-Prototypes and “blueprints” for hybrid experiences and installations (Authenticity Prototype, Caring Prototype, Open Space Museum / participation prototype).
 - Design and training resources (Design Toolbox, CoDesign Tool, guidelines & best practices, evaluation protocols).
- **Combination of public domain and in-copyright cultural heritage**

Many of the PERCEIVE case-study artworks are formally in the public domain but the **digital surrogates, analytical datasets and appearance measurements generated** around them are often **protected by copyright or neighbouring rights** and/or by the internal policies of the holding institutions (e.g. MUNCH, MANN, V&A, AIC), and negotiations with these partners have sometimes proved challenging. In defining its IPR strategy, PERCEIVE therefore had to carefully balance the EU principle that public domain content should remain in the public domain after digitisation with museums’ legitimate interests in controlling the reuse of high-value digital assets, recovering their investment in digitisation and analysis, and managing reputational risks; this required case-by-case solutions that respect both the legal framework and institutional policies while still enabling meaningful open access, research use and downstream exploitation of project results.
- **Tension between open science and commercial exploitation**

EU regulations and Horizon Europe rules encourage open access to publications and, where possible, to research data and software, promoting FAIR and reusable outputs; at the same time, as detailed in D8.2, PERCEIVE foresees sustainable exploitation via a SaaS-based PERCEIVE Platform, fee-based API/data access, and professional services such as training and consulting. This dual objective requires a clear and enforceable IP framework that distinguishes which components (e.g. publications, selected datasets, some software modules) can be openly licensed and under what terms, and which components must remain under controlled or commercial licences to support viable revenue models. The final IPR management strategy therefore explicitly aligns openness obligations with these exploitation

models, ensuring that compliance with EU open science principles does not undermine, but rather underpins, the long-term sustainability of the PERCEIVE Platform, its data services and associated professional offerings.

- **Multiple rights holders and joint ownership**

Background assets provided by partners and associated contributors remain under their ownership, in line with the definitions and access rights set out in the Grant Agreement and Consortium Agreement; at the same time, many PERCEIVE results are co-created (e.g. prototypes, platform components, datasets), giving rise to joint foreground IP that required careful management through the PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM), the Consortium Agreement and specific side agreements which are currently under negotiation. These instruments are used to document and clarify the respective ownership shares, access rights, licensing conditions and exploitation roles of the different partners, ensuring that co-created results can be exploited in a fair, transparent and sustainable way without undermining individual partners' background positions or the overall exploitation strategy described in D8.2.

- **Data protection and ethics**

Some datasets include personal data (e.g. user studies, evaluation results, usage analytics). These are primarily governed by GDPR and ethical approvals, but also interact with IPR (e.g. licence terms must not conflict with data protection or consent).

This final IPR management strategy therefore (i) defines **default ownership and licensing regimes per result category** (e.g. platform core and API, Color Knowledge Repository software and data, prototypes and hybrid experiences, Open Space Museum / engagement applications, Design Toolbox and CoDesign Tool, analytical and demonstrator tools, training and documentation, and datasets), clarifying for each whether it is owned individually or jointly and under which standard licence or access regime it will normally be made available; (ii) **links each IPR choice explicitly to the exploitation models described in D8.2**, in particular the PERCEIVE Platform operated as a SaaS offering, API- and data-based services (including premium “ground-truth” datasets), prototypes and hybrid experiences offered as blueprints and services to museums and creative industries, and the Design Toolbox/CoDesign Tool offered as free/academic resources with paid training and customisation; and (iii) **embeds all IPR decisions into the PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM)**, using the convergence process in Section 3.4 to record ownership, licences and access rights at asset level, to identify and resolve collisions between partners' intentions, and to ensure that any evolution of exploitation plans does not roll back previously agreed IPR consensus.

5.2 IPR regulation and result-specific strategy

5.2.1 General principles and governance

The following principles apply to all PERCEIVE results:

1. **Compliance with legal and contractual framework**

- All IPR management follows:
 - The Horizon Europe Grant Agreement and Model Grant Agreement rules.
 - The Consortium Agreement (CA).
 - Applicable EU and national IPR, cultural heritage and data protection laws (see Section 3.1).

- Where conflicts arise, the Grant Agreement and CA prevail.

2. Background vs foreground and access rights

In PERCEIVE, **background** denotes pre-existing assets (software, data, know-how) which remain owned by the partner that provides them; access rights to such background for project implementation and for the exploitation of results are granted only as specified in the Consortium Agreement (CA) and are documented in the “Background assets” register and the PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM). **Foreground** denotes new results created within PERCEIVE, which are owned by the partner or partners that generate them; where results are co-created, they constitute joint foreground and are co-owned under the rules set out in the CA and recorded with their ownership shares, access rights and intended licences in the P-IM.

- Partners grant each other the **minimum access rights** needed to:
 - Implement the project (royalty-free).
 - Exploit their own results after the project (under fair and reasonable conditions), in line with the CA.

3. Open by default, restricted where justified

Scientific publications follow an **open access** model (green or gold OA), as summarised in D8.2, Section 5. Data and software should be **as open as possible, as closed as necessary**, considering:

- Third-party rights and museum policies.
 - Privacy and ethical constraints.
 - The need to preserve exploitation potential (e.g. SaaS, training services).
- Where full openness is not possible, **tiered access** and **clear licence terms** are used.

4. IP Map and convergence process

All significant PERCEIVE results are registered and maintained in the PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM), as described in Sections 3.2.3 and 3.4, which provides a single, up-to-date overview of the project’s IP landscape. For each asset, the P-IM records whether it is background or foreground, its owner(s), the intended licence and exploitation route, as well as any collisions between partners’ intentions. The convergence steps carried out between M18 and M30 (and continued thereafter) were used to resolve blocking collisions, to confirm default licences per result category (see table below), and to ensure that any new IP needs or exploitation ideas could be integrated without rolling back previously achieved consensus on ownership, access rights and licensing.

5. IPR review before dissemination and publication

Any public dissemination of PERCEIVE results – including scientific publications, website content, open-source releases, exhibitions and demonstrations – is subject to a prior IP review by the IP Managers and the Project Management Board (PMB) to ensure that (i) no confidential background is disclosed without the explicit consent of the owning partner, (ii) no patentable or commercially sensitive information is irreversibly disclosed before appropriate protection or exploitation decisions are taken, and (iii) all applicable licence obligations and museum or data-provider policies are fully respected. The publication approval workflow described in D8.2, Section 5 is systematically applied and coordinated with the PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM), so that each dissemination action is checked against the recorded ownership, access rights and licensing intentions at asset level before being authorised.

5.2.2 PERCEIVE results and default IPR strategy

The table below summarises the **default IPR intentions** for the main PERCEIVE result categories, based on the results (tools, services, platform, API, Knowledge Repository, prototypes) and the exploitation plans in D8.2. Final details (e.g. exact licence variants, revenue sharing) will be validated through the P-IM and the convergence process.

Result category	Examples / scope	Primary IP type(s)	Default ownership (foreground)	Default licence / access regime	Main exploitation route (D8.2)
Platform core & backend services	PERCEIVE Platform backend, orchestration logic, integration components	Software, database schemas, know-how	Partners contributing to WP5/WP8 platform development (joint ownership where collaboratively developed)	Source code: generally closed; exposed via SaaS and API only. API specification and documentation: openly published (e.g. CC BY 4.0).	SaaS model (subscriptions, pay-as-you-go), professional services, integration with museums and SMEs.
PERCEIVE API	Unified API supporting platform tools and services	Software, API design, documentation	Same as platform core: WP5/WP8 technical partners	API endpoints: access via API keys under terms of use. Free tier for research/teaching; paid tiers for professional/commercial use.	Backbone for platform exploitation, integration by third-party developers (creative industries, museums' IT).
Color Knowledge Repository - Software	Repository front-end and back-end (based on InvenioRDM), configuration, custom modules	Software, configuration, documentation	Technical partners leading WP3 (with joint ownership for contributed modules)	Preference for open-source licence (e.g. MIT or Apache-2.0) for PERCEIVE-specific modules, to maximise uptake; contributions to InvenioRDM under its existing licence.	Adoption by other institutions as data management backend; consulting, hosting and integration services.
Color Knowledge Repository - data	2D/3D models, multispectral/spectral data, appearance measurements, metadata, analytical reports	Databases, datasets, copyright, related rights, database rights	Data providers (museums, labs, external contributors); PERCEIVE partners for data they generate	Tiered open data model: (1) Open scientific/technical datasets under CC BY 4.0 or CC BY SA 4.0 where no further restrictions apply; (2) Restricted or CC BY-NC-SA 4.0 / custom licences where required by museum policies; (3) Internal/embargoed datasets for	Open science, training of AI models, data services and premium data access (e.g. high-fidelity foreground-truth-models, see D8.2 Section 3.4).

<p>PERCEIVE Prototypes & hybrid experiences</p>	<p>Authenticity Prototype, Caring Prototype, Participation/Open Space Museum prototypes, installation code and assets</p>	<p>Software, designs, UX, audiovisual content, 3D assets, text</p>	<p>Partners leading/prototyping in WP6/WP4/WP5; joint ownership where co-created with museums</p>	<p>sensitive or pre-commercial content. Prototype concepts and high-level blueprints: open (e.g. CC BY 4.0) to support reuse. Implementation code/assets: default non-exclusive licences to museums involved and to PERCEIVE Platform (for demonstrations), wider reuse governed by partner-specific terms recorded in the P-IM.</p>	<p>Museum experiences (ticketed events, unique ‘œauthentic’ sessions), blueprint packages for other institutions and creative SMEs, demonstration content for the Platform.</p>
<p>Open Space Museum / Engagement Applications</p>	<p>Digital twins, engagement apps, remote participation tools</p>	<p>Software, UI/UX, content, data</p>	<p>WP6 partners (e.g. HSLU, creative SMEs) plus hosting institutions for content</p>	<p>Engagement app software: typically closed-source with free basic use for non-commercial engagement; extended/custom features under commercial licence. Content tied to specific collections follows museum policies (CC licences or custom).</p>	<p>Deployment in partner museums and adoption by external museums, B2B services for customisation and integration, Spin-Off definition</p>
<p>Design Toolbox & CoDesign Tool (paper + webapp)</p>	<p>CoDesign card game, canvases, game boards, digital collaborative webapp</p>	<p>Copyright in texts, graphics, game mechanics, software</p>	<p>Design/tool owners in WP5, with acknowledgement of prior GIFT Visitor Box open-source heritage</p>	<p>Paper toolkit: open licence (e.g. CC BY-NC-SA 4.0) to enable free printing and use in non-commercial contexts; commercial use subject to permission. Webapp: freemium SaaS - core use free for academia/heritage; premium collaborative and custom features under subscription.</p>	<p>Training, co-design services, SaaS-subscriptions, customised card sets and workflows for institutions and SMEs (see Appendix A of D8.2).</p>

Analytical & demonstrator tools	Color change simulation, KodaColor rating tool, other WP3/WP4/WP5 SW-solutions	Software, algorithms, UI, documentation	Technical partners developing each tool (often joint ownership)	For mature, reusable tools: preference for open-source for non-core components to encourage uptake (exact licence decided per tool via P-IM). For internal or pre-commercial modules: closed, accessible only via platform/API.	Demonstration of PERCEIVE capabilities, integration into PERCEIVE Platform as pay-per-use tools, open-source adoption by research community.
Documentation, training and know-how	Guidelines, manuals, tutorials, webinars, workshop materials, best practice documents	Copyright in texts and media	Authoring partners; joint where co-written	Default: open access under CC BY 4.0, unless third-party content imposes more restrictive terms. Some training formats (e.g. tailored consultancy, paid courses) may include non-public materials.	Capacity building for museums and creative industries; basis for paid training and consulting services.
External call datasets	Data contributed via PERCEIVE external calls (e.g. TAC-7 textile captures, autochromes, fresco datasets)	Databases, datasets, copyright, related rights	Original data owners (external institutions/companies)	Contributors keep ownership and grant PERCEIVE a non-exclusive, royalty-free licence for project use (research, demonstrations) as specified in call conditions (D8.2 Section 6). Any further commercial reuse beyond these terms requires explicit agreement with the data owner.	Training AI models, validation datasets for scientific outputs, potential future data licensing subject to separate agreements.

5.2.3 Access rights within the consortium

To support both implementation and exploitation, the PERCEIVE consortium ensures that each partner receives, as a minimum, royalty-free access to other partners' background and foreground needed to complete its project tasks, as stipulated in the **Consortium Agreement (CA)**. After the end of the project, each partner is also entitled to fair and reasonable access to foreground required to exploit its own results, subject to bilateral agreement where a result is not made openly available. Jointly owned results (e.g. platform core components, certain prototypes, shared datasets) are governed by the joint ownership provisions in the CA and, where necessary, by additional internal arrangements specifying aspects such as the division of maintenance tasks or revenue sharing for a specific SaaS offer. All these access and governance arrangements are documented in, and made transparent through, the PERCEIVE IP Map (P-IM), which is used to ensure that no partner's exploitation plans are blocked by unforeseen IP constraints.

5.2.4 Third-party access and licensing

Third-party access to PERCEIVE results (museums, creative SMEs, researchers, the public) will be granted under clear terms and conditions, consistent with the result-specific IPR strategy outlined above. For the **PERCEIVE Platform and API**, Terms of Use will define acceptable use, attribution requirements, pricing schemes (if any) and data protection obligations, with academic and heritage institutions potentially benefiting from preferential conditions such as free or discounted research/teaching tiers. Access to data in the **Color Knowledge Repository** will always be governed by explicit dataset-level licences (e.g. CC BY 4.0, CC BY-NC-SA 4.0, or proprietary terms), and where museums' or other data providers' policies require stricter conditions, these will override PERCEIVE defaults; in all cases, any reuse must respect attribution, non-commercial clauses where applicable, and prohibitions on re-identification of anonymised datasets. **Software tools and prototypes** will follow a mixed model in which open-source components are published via appropriate repositories (e.g. GitHub, GitLab) with clear licence files, while closed components are made available only through the **PERCEIVE Platform/API** or dedicated bilateral agreements. For **commercial exploitation**, licensing and service contracts with clients will explicitly reference the relevant foreground and background owners, define revenue models (licence fees, subscriptions, pay-per-use, etc.), and ensure that all obligations towards the EU (e.g. exploitation and dissemination requirements) and towards data providers (e.g. museums and external contributors) are fully respected.

5.2.5 Sustainability and alignment with exploitation plans

The IPR strategy in this section is designed to support the long-term sustainability of PERCEIVE beyond the project by enabling a **SaaS-based business model** for the PERCEIVE Platform and API (as outlined in D8.2, Section 3.3), **recognising data as a high-value asset** and establishing a framework that **combines open data where possible with premium, value-added datasets** where justified (D8.2, Section 3.4), making core design and training resources (such as the CoDesign Tool and Design Toolbox) reusable by the wider community while allowing partners to develop consultancy, training and customisation services around them, and leaving room for spin-offs, joint ventures or other commercial entities (as discussed in the strategic options in Section 3.5) to operate under clear and fair IP and licensing arrangements.

The PMB, together with the IP Managers monitor:

- The alignment between this IPR strategy, the evolving **PERCEIVE tools/results list**, and the **Exploitation Strategy Document (D8.2)**.

- The need for any updates to the P-IM and, where necessary, to the CA or additional bilateral agreements, to ensure that all Key Exploitable Results can be sustainably exploited while respecting legal, ethical and cultural heritage constraints.

References

Birch, J. (2012). Worldwide prevalence of red-green color deficiency. *JOSA A*, 29(3), 313-320.

Ciortan, I.-M., George, S., & Hardeberg, J. (2022). Better Sensors, Better Forgers: An Adversarial Loop. *Authenticity Studies. International Journal of Archaeology and Art*, 1(Authenticity Studies, Volume 1, Issue 1), 168–193.

Correa, C. M. (2000). *Intellectual property rights, the WTO and developing countries: the TRIPS agreement and policy options*. Zed books.

Council Directive (1993). 93/7/EEC from the 15th of March 1993 on the Return of Cultural Objects Unlawfully Removed from the Territory of a Member State. *Official Journal of the European Communities No. L*, 74(74), 34.

Lang, P. J., Bradley, M. M., & Cuthbert, B. N. (1998). Emotion and motivation: measuring affective perception. *Journal of Clinical Neurophysiology*, 15(5), 397-408.

Sabatinelli, D., Flaisch, T., Bradley, M. M., Fitzsimmons, J. R., & Lang, P. J. (2004). Affective picture perception: gender differences in visual cortex?. *Neuroreport*, 15(7), 1109-1112.

Tsivolas, T. (2014). *Law and Religious Cultural Heritage in Europe*. Springer.

Wirth, L. (2001). Copyright International Labour Organization 2001 First published 2001 Second impression 2001 Publications of the International Labour Office enjoy copyright under Protocol 2 of the Universal Copyright Convention. *Nevertheless, short excerpts from them may be reproduced without authorization*.

Annex 1. Risk Assessment Tool

Assessment scale

L	low
M	medium
H	high
E	extreme

Status scale

Current
Obsolete

Grade scale

A	neither likely, neither serious
B	likely, but not too serious
C	less likely, but serious
D	highly likely, highly serious

ID	Status	Date	Registered by	Risk	WP involved	Description	Assessment of Likelihood	Assessment of Seriousness	Grade (combined Likelihood and Seriousness)	Mitigation
Risk-1	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Coordination Failure	WP1	There is a critical risk that coordination in WP1 may fail to effectively manage the project.	L	E	C	The coordination is divided into financial and administrative aspects, as well as scientific coordination. Additionally, an innovation manager is appointed to enhance overall project management.
Risk-2	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Terminology Issues	WP2	Misunderstandings among consortium partners about the meaning of words & terms.	H	M	B	To address this issue, a glossary will be created with a taxonomy and definitions of all words & terms that are possibly subject to misinterpretation among consortium partners.
Risk-3	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Wrongly Elaborated Requirements	WP2	A potential risk in WP2 involves the wrongly elaborated requirements.	M	M	B	To address this, the project adopts an iterative path to understand end users' needs. Mitigation includes expanding stakeholder involvement, considering third parties and advisory board partners to set up target groups, and providing specific training for museum staff to guide and control project phases effectively.

Risk-4	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Limited Data Acquisition	WP3	WP3 faces a risk of limited data acquisition for training datasets.	L	E	C	Mitigation involves partners exploring other institutions for dataset examples, engaging associated and third parties interested in data sharing. Additionally, a call for participation is initiated to address the issue.
Risk-5	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Insufficient Training Data	WP4	There is a risk of insufficient training data in WP4.	M	H	C	Proposed mitigation measures include improving training datasets with synthetically generated data. An open call by the consortium aims to populate the training data with external sources. If the database remains small, the IBR core is designed to mitigate the risk using established solutions.
Risk-6	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Insufficient NN Performance	WP4	WP4 faces the risk of insufficient Neural Network (NN) performance.	H	H	D	Mitigation involves redesigning the network architecture, incorporating research advances, and considering suggestions from the advisory board.
Risk-7	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Delays Due to WP Dependencies	WP7 WP5 WP4	A potential risk in WP5 is delays due to dependencies on WP3 and WP4 outcomes. WP7 is dependent on WP5 and WP6.	H	H	D	Mitigation strategies include the detailed planning that was defined during the PERCEIVE kick-off meeting, an iterative approach, and delivering preliminary results to other tasks and work packages in advance. The WP structure ensures early, simultaneous, and independent development, facilitating fast prototyping despite dependencies.

Risk-4	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Limited Data Acquisition	WP3	WP3 faces a risk of limited data acquisition for training datasets.	L	E	C	Mitigation involves partners exploring other institutions for dataset examples, engaging associated and third parties interested in data sharing. Additionally, a call for participation is initiated to address the issue.
Risk-5	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Insufficient Training Data	WP4	There is a risk of insufficient training data in WP4.	M	H	C	Proposed mitigation measures include improving training datasets with synthetically generated data. An open call by the consortium aims to populate the training data with external sources. If the database remains small, the IBR core is designed to mitigate the risk using established solutions.
Risk-6	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Insufficient NN Performance	WP4	WP4 faces the risk of insufficient Neural Network (NN) performance.	H	H	D	Mitigation involves redesigning the network architecture, incorporating research advances, and considering suggestions from the advisory board.
Risk-7	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Delays Due to WP Dependencies	WP7 WP5 WP4	A potential risk in WP5 is delays due to dependencies on WP3 and WP4 outcomes. WP7 is dependent on WP5 and WP6.	H	H	D	Mitigation strategies include the detailed planning that was defined during the PERCEIVE kick-off meeting, an iterative approach, and delivering preliminary results to other tasks and work packages in advance. The WP structure ensures early, simultaneous, and independent development, facilitating fast prototyping despite dependencies.
Risk-12	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Unavailable hardware	WP3	Difficulties in finding a hardware configuration fully compatible with PERCEIVE.	M	M	B	Mitigation rely on the capability of the researchers among consortium partners to come up with customized and/or in-house solutions.
Risk-13	Current	2024-01-30	NTNU	Difficulties in Spin-off Creation	WP8	There is a risk of difficulties in creating a spin-off in WP8.	E	H	D	Mitigation involves relying on commercial partners for the commercialization and economic exploitation of project results if a dedicated team for spin-off creation cannot be found.